

Conception of Jain Materiality and the Composition of Jain Worlds

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Abstract

Religious materialism cannot be estranged from its immateriality. Jain cosmology perceives its biotic and abiotic worlds and the related matters and components from its theological treatises and interpretations. In the Jain world where we live, it is conflowed with the related time cycle. All Jain worlds are not connected with this time cycle. Jainism uses a specific term 'Pudgala,' which is commonly used by all variants of the śramaṇic tradition. However, as a generic term it has some features that resemble other branches of śramaṇic School. But in Jainism this term implies some distinctive attributes of Jain materiality too. In this article Jain materiality and the composition of the Jain material world will be explained and elucidated using the necessary Jain texts, exegeses, interpretations, both old and new. Jain cosmology will be explained here too as Jain materiality is connected with this.

Śramaṇic tradition and its material world:

From the Jain texts it is tangible that Jain perception of the world is composed of traditional Hindu concepts and the rival śramaṇic traditions. The historical rivalry started some 6th century BCE based on some specific questions and arguments that eventually helped the protagonists of the movement confuting, refuting and rejecting some traditional beliefs and abolishing some canonical laws of Hinduism. As a result, the history of Indian philosophy was bifurcated and two parallel fluxes have been flowing till today. For better understanding of the śramaṇic worldview we have to dive into the depth of this tradition. The term *śramaṇa*

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refers to a person who labours, toils, or exerts himself for some higher or religious purpose. Lecture XXXII of *Uttaradhyāyana Sūtra* titled the ‘Causes of Carelessness’ recalls some of the sanctions we came across in *Ācāraṅga Sūtra*:

“A Sramana engaged in penance, should not allow himself to watch the shape, beauty, coquetry, laughter, prattle, gestures, and glances of women, nor retain a recollection of them in his mind.” (Müller 2002: Vol 45: 176)

The Jain *śramaṇas* want to ensure the efficacy of their dispassionate state of mind through the above Sutra, through which they want to prove their rational apprehension and worldview too. But Jains have their own logical framework and parameter to understand cosmos and this world. Like Hinduism and Buddhism, the universe is infinite in Jainism. Like Hinduism and Buddhism Jains believe that universe has been existing eternally; it has neither beginning nor end and time is cyclical. And therefore, one after another time cycle has been emerging. Hence, we can deduce that the concept of Jain time-space continuum has emerged from the Indic understanding.

It is to be noted that although in Hinduism the cyclic time-space continuum is eternal, it can be bookended by any unprecedented event. Jain time-space continua are running one after another without any cease or change like Buddhism (Dickstein 2024). The time cycle is called here *Kalpakāla*. Kalpa is here Jain unit of time. The *Kalpas* regulate the classical Jain cosmography (Dickstein 2024).

Jain Time cycle and Jain Time-Space Continua

In Jainism ‘Time’ and ‘Space’ are very important to determine the objective phenomenon. Bhattacharya has written that the spatial (*Kṣetra*), the temporal (*Kāla*), the essential (*Dravya*) and the modal (*Bhāva*) relationships between objects and objective phenomena constitute the Jain objective realities. They are not dependent on the knowing subjects; the knowing subjects can only know those objective realities, what the aforementioned factors constitute. They can also modify their nature. So, if experience and reason make someone to understand any object, one will understand that on the basis of its particular nature, location, mode, time and so forth (Bhattacharya 1953: 60-61). So, those who live in this time-spatial continuum, even if they understand their phenomenon objectively, this understanding may not lead them to understand the totality.

Jain cosmology perceives a wheel of time, which is divided into two halves: *Utsarpiṇī* or ascending part of the time cycle and *Avasarpiṇī*, the descending part of the time cycle. Each consists of 10 x 1 crore x 1 crore *Addhāsāgaropama* (10 *kotikoṭī Sāgaropama*). Thus, one cycle of time (*Kalpakāla*) gets over in 20 *kotikoṭī Sāgaropama* (Samantabhadra 2016: 71). The current one is an *Avasarpiṇī*. In each half of the cosmic time cycle exactly twenty-four *Tīrthaṅkaras* grace this part of the universe. The first *Tīrthaṅkara* in this present time cycle (Hunda *Avasarpiṇī*) was Ṛṣabhadeva, who is credited for formulating and organizing human beings to live in a society harmoniously. The 24th and the last *Tīrthaṅkara* of the present half-cycle was Mahāvīra (599 BC–527 BC). It is even recorded in the modern history that Mahāvīra and his predecessor, Pārśvanātha, the twenty-third *Tīrthaṅkara* existed in the world (nowshad Oct-Dec 2023: Vol 61: Issue 23: 26-27).

The Jain Time Cycles are morally conditioned. Lawrence A. Babb vividly described that,

“As just mentioned, change is not a feature of the Jain cosmos as a whole; rather, cyclical movements occur only in certain small areas of the cosmos of which the part of the world we inhabit is one example. The cycle consists of periods of improvement and decline in an endless succession. An *utsarpiṇī* (ascending epoch) begins in a condition of moral and physical squalor. As things gradually improve, the moral and physical condition of human beings strengthens and nature becomes kinder and more bountiful; at the cycle’s high point the world is a paradise. Then begins an *avasarpiṇī* (an epoch of gradual decline) in which all of the attainments of the previous epoch are gradually undone until the cycle bottoms out and a new ascending epoch begins. We are currently in a declining epoch. A complete cycle is known as a *kalpa*.”(Lawrence 2015: 106-7)

Each half-cycle of time has been subdivided to indicate six distinct phases of wellbeing. This wellbeing indicated the welfare of all beings; naturally it includes human beings or Anthropos. This can be understood by an Aristotelian term ‘eudaimonia’. But Jain wellbeing includes all beings and entities at a time. It can draw a fare debate how two opponents could be benefitted if we want to understand from the idea of *Pareto Optimality*. The concept explicitly expresses that if all possible Pareto improvements have been accomplished in a society and no option remains left that can make anyone benefitted through any means, it is not possible to make anyone further better-off without making someone worse-off. However, we can guess that a particular theology explains a being or a group as ‘good’ or ‘evil’ from its understanding. So,

it is putative here that ‘the good tidings’ would be ensured for those who are good, just and righteous from the Jain vantage point.

Utsarpiṇī’s first phase is very miserable and gloomy, which is called *duṣamā-duṣamā*. Then with the lapse of time the tide of absolute misery lessens and the phase *duṣamā* begins. Here misery is comparative low. Then a new phase called *duṣamā-suṣamā* follows it, when misery starts to end and happiness starts to prevail but welfare does not triumph wholeheartedly. Then a new sun of hope rises on the horizon. Hence, more happiness and welfare prevail over evil and unhappiness, but they cannot diminish the darkness sides entirely. This phase is called *suṣamā-duṣamā*. A positive phase with bounties of welfare and happiness follows it. This phase is called *suṣamā*. Finally, the long awaited absolute positive phase of welfare and all good tidings emerge. All evils get vanquished by all means. This phase is called *suṣamā-suṣamā* (Dickstein 2024).

Thereafter, the reverse order starts, which is called the *Avasarpiṇī*. The six phases move with a reverse current. Twenty-four *Tīrthaṅkaras* or the “ford makers” and supreme spiritual teachers according to Jainism appear during both *Utsarpiṇī* and *Avasarpiṇī* halves. Dickstein has deduced the fact that the *Tīrthaṅkaras* never appear in the “very happy” or “very unhappy” phases of the *kalpa*, as well as in some other phases. These phases are too uncongenial to ensure the flux of dharma because inverse relationship between extreme happiness and the urge of *mokṣa*, and extreme unhappiness and the ability to pursue *mokṣa* (Dickstein 2024). Lawrence A. Babb wrote,

“Precisely twenty-four *Tīrthaṅkaras* appear in each *utsarpiṇī* and *avasarpiṇī* epoch. *Tīrthaṅkaras* are born only in the second, third and fourth eras of a *utsarpiṇī* epoch and the third and fourth of an *avasarpiṇī* epoch. They do not appear during the extremes of happiness or unhappiness because too much happiness discourages the sense of urgency about liberation required to motivate ascetic practices, and too much unhappiness means that humans are too miserable to pursue liberation by engaging in such practices. Our current era in our *avasarpiṇī* is the fifth, and therefore no *Tīrthaṅkaras* will appear and nobody will achieve liberation (in our corner of the terrestrial world) until the next *utsarpiṇī* is well under way.” (Lawrence 2015: 107)

According to Jain cosmology human beings and other biotic and abiotic entities that we see live in the middle-world, which is called *Madhyaloka* in Jain parlance. It is a familiar Indic term as well. Our living space or ‘lebensraum’ is surrounded by an ocean. The centre of this earthy living place is called *Jambudvīpa*, literally means ‘Rose Apple Island’. It has seven zones or *kṣetras*. Only two of them are subject to ebb and flow of this cosmic time. These two zones are *Bharataḥkṣetra* and *Airāvataḥkṣetra*. The time cycles are attuned with ebb and low tides. The *Kalpas* do not function in the upper world or *ūrdhvaloka* or lower world or *adholoka* (Dickstein 2024).

Jainism believes in rebirth and reincarnation. Lawrence A. Babb has described the structure of the Jain cosmos.

“It is a vertical structure, taller than it is wide, widest at the bottom, and vast in extent. Outside of it is merely non-cosmos. Its overall shape is not unlike the outline of a human figure standing with arms akimbo and legs spread, which indeed is how it is sometimes represented in artistic portrayals. This entire cosmos swarms with an ‘infinite’ (*ananta*, as opposed to *asaṅkhyata*, ‘uncountable’) number of living things, which occupy its every cranny. Running from the very top to the bottom is a shaft known as the *trasa nāḍī*, so named because *trasa* (mobile beings with two or more senses) can live only within its boundaries. The simplest forms of life – the single-sensed *nigodas* and element beings – are found both within and outside the *trasa nāḍī* and occupy the cosmos to its very outer boundaries. At the very top of the cosmos is *siddha loka* or *siddha śilā* (a small zone shaped as an upward-facing crescent) where liberated souls abide eternally in omniscient bliss.” (Lawrence 2015: 110-11)

Jain writings and traditions have emphasized on the structural precision of the cosmos. The height of the entire cosmos is given in a unit of distance, which is called the *rajju* (rope). It is said the height of the cosmos is fourteen *rajjus*. One account informs us that a *rajju* is equal to the distance covered by a god flying for six months at the rate of 2,057,152 *yojanas* per second (Caillat; Kumar 1981: 20).

The cosmos has three subdivisions. In-between the upper world and the lower a thin disc known as *madhya-loka* (middle world), and it is the abode of the human beings. Below the disc there is a hellish region called *adho-loka* (lower world). Above the disc a heavenly region is existing, called *ūrdhva-loka* (upper world). The depth of the lower *adho-loka* is seven *rajjus* and there it has seven layers of hell (Lawrence 2015: 111-12).

Pic: The Jain Cosmos

Jain biotic and abiotic entities

Jain microcosms and macrocosms are constituted of *Pudgala*, something which is supposed to be alike atom but can form non-substantial matters and entities. In Jain ontology *Pudgala* has been constituted of two words; *Pud* and *Gala*. The words mean fusion and fission respectively. *Pud* involves the association or fusion of material and immaterial substances, which are called *Dravya* in Sanskrit language. *Gala* means dissociation or disintegration of matters or substances from one another. In Jainims *Pudgala* refers to *Rūpi-ajīvas* or the non-sentient or non-living substances. The fusions and fissions occur both among the *Jīvās* or the sentient beings or substances and the *Pudgalas*. *Pudgalas* fall in the ambit of the *Ājīvas* (Sharma 1997: 63). The human deeds have shapes through these associations and dissociations (Saran Jain). This is the process that the Karmic world has been formed

according to Jainism. The absolute *Pudgala* (absolute non-sentient substance) does not belong to the Karmic world. It does not experience any rebirth and reincarnation.

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